

The Gini Index of Starlike Trees

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Abstract. Gini index is used in the economy to measure the income inequality of social groups. The graph theoretical applications of Gini index for rooted trees was introduced in 2017. For this purpose, two distance based topological indices (level index and Gini index) were introduced. In this paper, we compute the level index and Gini index of starlike trees.

Keywords. Gini index, Level index, Starlike tree, Probability

1. Introduction

The Gini index was defined by Corrado Gini in 1912.^[1] It shows the income inequality of social groups and is used by The World Bank for the economical investigations. The graph theoretical application of Gini index introduced by Balaji and Mahmoud in 2017^[2] for rooted trees. They introduced two distance based topological indices, level index and Gini index. Moreover, degree based Gini index was defined by Domicolo and Mahmoud in 2019.^[3] The statistical applications of degree and distance based Gini indices were made for random caterpillar graphs.^[4,5]

The first distance based topological index was introduced by Wiener in 1947.^[6] Nano-scientific developments about Wiener index were presented by Ottorino Ori in 2020.^[7] More details about Wiener index can be found in the survey.^[8] Moreover, distance based information indices were calculated for some classes of graphs.^[9,10]

In this paper, we study the level index and Gini index of starlike trees. It is known that a starlike tree is a special tree which has only one vertex of degree at least 3. Starlike trees have more investigated in mathematical chemistry. For example, the Wiener index was studied^[11]

and Hosoya index of was investigated.^[12] The connectivity index of starlike trees was studied in the paper.^[13] Moreover the extremal values of some vertex degree based topological indices were calculated for starlike trees.^[14]

2. Preliminaries

We use only simple, connected and undirected graphs. The degree of a vertex u is denoted by $\deg(u)$. The notation $d(u, v)$ is used to show the distance between two any vertices u and v in a graph.

In a graph G , the number of vertices n is called order. The path graphs with n vertices are denoted by P_n .

Definition 2.1. The total distance from a vertex $u \in V(G)$ to other vertices is presented by the following phrase

$$D(u) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} d(u, v).$$

Definition 2.2. The Wiener index for a graph G is defined by the following equation^[6]

$$W(G) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{u \in V(G)} D(u).$$

Definition 2.3. The Wiener index of a path graph P_n is given by the following equation^[8]

$$W(P_n) = \binom{n+1}{3}.$$

3. Level Index and Gini Index

Balaji and Mahmoud introduced two distance based topological indices for rooted trees.^[2] The first one is called level index and level index of a tree is denoted by $L(T)$. Level index of a tree T is computed by the following equation

$$L(T) = \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} |D_j(T) - D_i(T)|$$

such that $D_i(T)$ and $D_j(T)$ showing the vertices at distances i and j from the central vertex of the tree T .

Moreover the Gini index of a tree T is denoted by $G(T)$ and it is computed by the following equation

$$G(T) = \frac{L(T)}{(E[|T|])^2 E[D_T^*]}$$

$E[|T|]$ equals to n for a single tree. Moreover, $E[D_T^*]$ shows the average distance of vertices with respect to the distances of vertices from the central vertex. Then, it is computed by

$$E[D_T^*] = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n D_i(T)}{n}$$

where $D_i(T)$ showing the vertices at distances i from the central vertex of the tree T . In order to exemplify the level index and Gini index, we use the example given in the paper.^[2]

Figure 1. The tree T which is used in the following example

Example 3.1. The Gini index of the tree T of Figure 1 is computed as follows. The average distance

$$E[D_T^*] = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n D_i(T)}{n} = \frac{0 + (1 + 1) + (2 + 2 + 2)}{6} = \frac{4}{3}$$

and the level index of T is computed by

$$L(T) = 1 + 1 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 = 14.$$

Then, it is obtained that

$$G(T) = \frac{L(T)}{(E[|T|])^2 E[D_T^*]} = \frac{14}{6^2 \times 4/3} = \frac{7}{24}.$$

4. Starlike Graphs

A starlike graph $T(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ is consisted of a central vertex u of degree $u > 2$ and k branches with the property

$$T(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k) - u = P_{n_1} \cup P_{n_2} \cup \dots \cup P_{n_k}$$

where $n_1 \geq n_2 \geq \dots \geq n_k \geq 1$. It implies that the starlike tree $T(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ has k branches with the lengths n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k , respectively.

Two starlike trees are illustrated in Figure 2. The first one is $T(4, 3, 2, 2)$. The second one is consisted of two paths P_r by sharing a common vertex which is the m -th vertex of these paths. The Hosoya indices and Merrifield-Simmons indices of this family ordered in the paper.^[15] For $2 \leq m \leq r - 1$, $T(m - 1, m - 1, r - m, r - m)$ is a starlike tree.

Figure 2. Starlike trees $T(4, 3, 2, 2)$ and $T(m - 1, m - 1, r - m, r - m)$

5. Main Results

In this section we obtain the main results of the paper. We calculate the level index and Gini index for starlike trees.

Lemma 5.1. Let T be a rooted tree. Then,

$$L(T) \leq W(T)$$

with the equality if and only if $T = P_n$

Proof. Because of a path $P_n: v_1 v_2 \dots v_n$ is a linear graph, there exists one vertex for each distance from v_1 . Then, the distances between the levels are changed to distances between the vertices. By this way we obtain that

$$L(P_n) = W(P_n).$$

Now assume that $T \neq P_n$. It means that there is a vertex v of T whose degree is at least three. If v is on the k -level, there are at least two vertices x, y on $(k + 1)$ -level. Since, x and y are on the same level, the distance between these vertices equals to zero for level index. However, for

the Wiener index the distance between these vertices is two. Then, it is obtained that $L(T) < W(T)$.

Theorem 5.2. Let $T = T(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ be a starlike tree. Then, the level index of T is presented by the following equation

$$L(T) = \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i+1}) + (k - 1) \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i}) - \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq k} W(P_{j-i}).$$

Proof. In the beginning, we compute the level index of vertices which are existed on the same branch. By Lemma 5.1, we know that the level index of paths equals to Wiener index of them. With the vertex central vertex u , level index for each one of the k branches equals to Wiener index. Each branch of T is assumed a path P_{n_i+1} with the central vertex u ($1 \leq i \leq k$). Then, we obtain the level index of the vertices which are existed on the same branch as

$$\sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i+1}).$$

We can compute the level index of vertices which are existed in different branches. Assume that P_{n_1} and P_{n_2} are two branches of T such that $P_{n_1}: x_1x_2 \dots x_{n_1}$ and $P_{n_2}: y_1y_2 \dots y_{n_2}$. We investigate two cases.

First Case. We compute the distances from the vertices of P_{n_1} to P_{n_2} . The vertices x_1 and y_1 are on the same level. Then, the distance is 0 for level index. The distance between x_1 and y_2 is 1 and finally the distance between x_1 and y_{n_2} is $n_2 - 1$. Then, it is understood that the contribution of x_1 to level index equals to contribution of y_1 . By this way, it is obtained that the first n_2 vertices of the P_{n_1} have the same contributions to the level index as much as the vertices of P_{n_2} such that $W(P_{n_2})$. Since $n_1 \geq n_2$, the remaining $n_1 - n_2$ vertices of P_{n_1} has zero level index on P_{n_2}

Second Case. We compute the distances from the vertices of P_{n_2} to P_{n_1} . The distance between y_1 and x_2 is 1, the distance between y_1 and x_3 is 2. Finally, the distance between y_1 and x_{n_1} is $n_1 - 1$. Since $n_1 \geq n_2$, the contributions of the vertices of P_{n_2} to the level index as much as the first n_2 vertices of P_{n_1} such that $W(P_{n_1}) - W(P_{n_1-n_2})$.

Then we obtain the level index between the branches P_{n_1} and P_{n_2} as in the following phrase

$$W(P_{n_1}) + W(P_{n_2}) - W(P_{n_1-n_2}).$$

There are $k - 1$ binary subsets of branches which contain a branch P_{n_i} for $1 \leq i \leq k$. Then the level index of starlike tree T is presented by the following equation

$$L(T) = \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i+1}) + (k - 1) \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i}) - \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq k} W(P_{j-i}).$$

Then, the proof is completed.

Example 5.3. The Level index of $T = T(m - 1, m - 1, r - m, r - m)$ which is illustrated in Figure 2 is

$$L(T) = 2W(P_m) + 2W(P_{r-m+1}) + 6W(P_{m-1}) + 6W(P_{r-m}) - 4W(P_{2m-r+1}).$$

Lemma 5.4. If the lengths of the branches of the starlike tree $T(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ are equal as $n_1 = n_2 = \dots = n_k = m$, then the level index is computed by the following equation

$$L(T) = kW(P_{m+1}) + (k^2 - k)W(P_m).$$

Proof. By Theorem 5.2, Level index of starlike tree $T = T(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ is computed by

$$L(T) = \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i+1}) + (k - 1) \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i}) - \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq k} W(P_{j-i}).$$

We have k branches P_m , then

$$\begin{aligned} L(T) &= \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{m+1}) + (k - 1) \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_m) \\ &= kW(P_{m+1}) + (k^2 - k)W(P_m). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 5.5. Let $T = T(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_k)$ be a starlike tree. Then, the Gini index of T is presented by the following equation

$$G(T) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i+1}) + (k - 1) \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i}) - \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq k} W(P_{j-i})}{n \sum_{i=1}^k n_i(n_i + 1)/2}$$

Proof. By Theorem 5.2, level index of the starlike tree T is

$$L(T) = \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i+1}) + (k - 1) \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i}) - \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq k} W(P_{j-i}).$$

Moreover, the $E[|T|]$ and average distance $E[D_T^*]$ with respect to the central vertex u equal to

$$E[|T|] = n,$$

$$E[D_T^*] = \frac{1}{n} (1 + 2 + \dots + n_1 + \dots + 1 + 2 + \dots + n_k)$$

$$= \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{n_i(n_i + 1)}{2}.$$

By this way, we obtain the Gini index of the starlike tree T as in the following equation

$$G(T) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_{i+1}}) + (k-1) \sum_{i=1}^k W(P_{n_i}) - \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq k} W(P_{j-i})}{n \sum_{i=1}^k n_i(n_i + 1)/2}.$$

6. Conclusion

The standart Gini index is an important tool for economical investigations. After the graph theoretical application of Gini index by Balaji and Mahmoud,^[2] it is used to evaluate for capturing the balance in a tree.

In this paper, we calculate the level index and Gini index of starlike trees. The statistical analysis of the mentioned trees can be made by these formulas.

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